

FATIGUE MECHANISMS DESCRIPTION IN SHORT GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC BY MICROTOMOGRAPHIC OBSERVATIONS

H. Rolland¹, N. Saintier¹ and G. Robert²

¹I2M, Arts et Métiers ParisTech
Esplanade des Arts et Métiers 33405 Talence, France
Email: heloise.rolland@ensam.eu

²Solvay Engineering Plastics
Avenue Ramboz, BP 64, 69192 Saint-Fons, France

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ABSTRACT

Short glass fibre reinforced thermoplastics are promising materials for weight reduction of structures thanks to its very good specific mechanical properties. The current challenge is to provide experimental data concerning damage mechanisms and their kinetics in order to enhance micromechanical models for these materials with complex behaviour. The objective of this work is therefore to observe and explain damage mechanisms regarding spatial configuration of the microstructure. Fatigue tests have been running on reinforced polyamide specimens and interrupted at different levels of the estimated life. 3D pictures of the gage length of these specimens have been obtained by microtomography with high resolution (0.65 μm). This data presents damage location at different stages of lifetime. Thus, debonding, matrix cavitation and fibre failure have been identified as the three damage mechanisms for these materials. The analysis of the evolution of the damage markers quantity, volume and aspect ratio inform about the kinetic for each mechanism during the material life.

1 INTRODUCTION

With increasing constraints of lightening in industrial fields, mechanical properties are now considered regarding material density. This trend ranks the short glass fibre reinforced polyamide 6,6 among very promising materials, whence emerges the need to describe its intricate behaviour. This complexity mainly comes from the microstructure of the material: the injection process, perfectly suited for high productivity and complex shapes, induces heterogeneous distribution and orientation of fibres. Furthermore, the mechanical performance of these composites results from a combination of the fibre and matrix properties and the ability to transfer stresses across the fibre–matrix interface as indicated by Thomason's works [1,2]

In order to model its behaviour, one can use micromechanical approach which requires damage mechanisms knowledge and strain and stress thresholds values. The objective is then to observe and localise damage initiation and its development in the reinforced polymer. Despite significant work, there still is a lack of data about the link between spatial configuration of this microstructure fibres and damage mechanisms. Reference work in the field results from scanning electron microscopy (SEM) observations and analysis: a description of damage chronology has been made by Horst [3,4] for fatigue stress. Failure scenario in fatigue has been described by following steps: 1) Initiation of damage at the fibre ends. 2) Growth of this damage into voids, accompanied by debonding. 3) The voids grow into microcracks, which may remain bridged by either drawn matrix material or unbroken fibres. 4) The debonding relieves the constraint to which the matrix was subjected, which can therefore deform much more easily, forming bridges between the crack walls. 5) The bridged crack grows, until a critical size is reached, and the specimen fails.

Two points have to be underlined about this work: firstly, the evolution of material process technology has to be considered. Then, this is a partial observation: SEM tool only enables surface observation. For this reason, it is maybe not representative of mechanisms proportions and kinetics in the whole material. In accordance to the objective of the study (i.e. spatial configuration of damage with respect to fibre organization), microtomography is the most suitable tool for 3D damage observation.

Here are presented the specific features of the material. Then, the procedure to manage to observe fatigue damage in the volume of the material is explained. This part is followed by a summary of preliminary results obtained with this method. Finally, results obtained for fatigue tests are shown and discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Microtomography

X-ray computed microtomography is an observation technic based on the acquisition of a certain number of X-ray radiographs obtained for different angular positions of the sample with respect to the beam. These sets of X-ray radiographs are put together to obtain the three dimensional distribution of the linear X-ray attenuation coefficient μ within the sample. This distribution forms a 3D image where the elementary unit is called a voxel (*volumetric pixel*). For the reconstruction step, an analytical method was used. This method is faster than algebraic ones, but requires a complete set of radiographs during the rotation and cannot deal with missing views [5].

X-ray computed microtomography can be performed using microfocus and synchrotron X-ray sources. Experiments presented in this paper were performed on ID19 beamline at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (Grenoble, France). A pink X-ray beam was used in mode 16 bunches, with a photon energy of 19 keV. A PCO edge camera with a 2048 x 2048 pixel sensor received 6000 X-ray radiographs during a rotation of the specimen over 180° along vertical axis. This experimental setup was optimized to obtain a voxel edge size of 0.65 μm . The acquisition of a complete scan lasts about 7 minutes.

2.2 Specimen

The studied material is Technyl® A218V30, a commercial grade of polyamide 6,6 reinforced by 30wt% of short glass fibre supplied by Solvay Engineering Plastics-France. In addition to an intricate behaviour, the matrix of this material shows sensitivity to its conditioning. Indeed, effect of water content on polyamide 6,6 mechanical properties has been demonstrated [6,7]. For this reason, water content for specimens of the study has been fixed at 50% of relative humidity (RH50), by immersion in a controlled temperature and climate chamber at 80°C, 60% of humidity during 96 hours.

Fibres have a constant diameter of 10 μm . Their length is distributed between 100 μm and 800 μm . Their orientation is heterogeneous in the thickness of the specimen: a core-shell-skin structure is induced by the injection process used to form rectangular plates. This structure, typically observed for injection moulded short fibres reinforced thermoplastics, is characterised by three distinguishable layers: core, shell, skin. This structure is illustrated by figure 1.

Figure 1: Core-shell-skin structure in the thickness of the specimen

The skin layer is due to the thermal shock between the injected material and the mould walls. Fibres are frozen in their position and orientation forming a 100 μ m thick layer of randomly oriented fibres. The shell layer is the largest with a thickness of 1.4 mm. In this layer, a shear stress of the material flow orientates fibres in the mould flow direction (MFD). The core is 300 μ m thick in the centre of the specimen. Contrary to the shell, fibres are there perpendicular to the MFD. This orientation is due to an extensional flow during the injection process [8]. This structure induces anisotropy of mechanical properties. For the study, three sampling orientations have been chosen: specimens are 0°, 45° or 90° to MFD.

3D X-ray microtomography has a limited size of observation, depending on resolution and sensor size. In this case, the observed zone is a cube of 1.66 mm edge size. This constraint leads to define particular specimen geometry: the size of the gage length had to be equivalent to observable volume with microtomography. As specimens were watercut from plates of 3.24 mm thickness and since a square material section helps microtomography process, the geometry of the specimen has been determined as presented in figure 2:

Figure 2: Specimen geometry

With this geometry, the gage length is slightly superior to the observed zone, but priority was to preserve the core-shell-skin symmetry of the specimen.

2.3 Procedure

The study has been designed to observe fatigue damage mechanisms. In order to generate complementary data, fatigue tests have been running and interrupted at different levels of their estimated life. For a given life time, four specimens have been observed: a non-fatigued reference and three specimens interrupted at 50%, 75% and 95% of the estimated life. Fatigue tests were performed on a BOSE electroforce machine of 7.5kN capacity. A 3Hz frequency has been chosen, sufficiently low to avoid self-heating phenomena. The load ratio is $R = 0.1$. The stress level has been determined to reach a 50 000 cycles life time.

Figure 3: Experimental set-up on ID19 beamline - ESRF

During the microtomography process, specimens were maintained under stress (limited to half maximal stress of the fatigue test) by a compact tensile machine in order to facilitate observation of damages in the material. This machine (presented in figure 3) has been especially designed for this experiment with X-ray microtomography. At the height of the specimen gage length, the machine part is a thin and homogeneous part of PMMA to minimize attenuation of the set-up. The displacement is controlled by a step motor and the load measured with a load cell.

3 PRELIMINARY RESULTS ON ANALYSIS OF DAMAGE MARKERS MORPHOLOGY

Series of tensile tests on this material had been observed with the same procedure in a previous work [9]. The analysis of this data allowed to distinguish three main damage mechanisms: fibre failure, matrix damage, damage at the fibre-matrix interface (including debonding and damage initiation at fibre ends). Each mechanism has been associated with damage markers geometric measurements. Indeed, fibre failures (figure 4a) are linked with non-spherical damage markers having a width inferior to fibre diameter. Debonding concerns lengthened damage markers, as illustrated in figure 4b. This feature can be quantified by the ratio between the length and the width of the marker: the aspect ratio. Fibre end markers are rather spherical, so they have a low aspect ratio and their length is equivalent or inferior to fibres diameter. Matrix damage is associated to damage markers with an important volume. As indicated in figure 4d, the minimal volume to enter this category is equivalent to the volume of a sphere with a diameter of 1.5 times the fibres diameter.

Figure 4: Damage markers geometry associated with damage mechanisms

This classification of the different damage markers allow to quantitatively distinguish mechanisms in the observed volumes, as presented in figure 5. The threshold value to decide between debonding and other mechanisms has been chosen at 4, based on observations of each 3D volume, to be systematically representative of this mechanism.

Figure 5: Quasi-static mechanisms classification based on geometrical aspects of damage markers

From this classification, it has been possible to determine the evolution of each mechanism during an *in situ* tensile test. These results are presented in figure 6. The observed volume measured 0.6 mm^3 and has shown a fibre density of 9403 fibres per mm^3 at the beginning of the test, to reach 13 963 fibres per mm^3 as specimen failure approaches. This preliminary study confirms the possibility of the use of microtomography to identify damage mechanism and of the quantitative analysis on damage markers to identify mechanisms kinetics.

Figure 6 : Damage markers evolution per mechanism during a tensile test

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Observed fatigue mechanisms

The observed mechanisms are slightly different between fatigue and quasi-static stresses. Indeed, if damage at the fibre-matrix interface (debonding and damage at fibre ends) and fibre failure are common damage mechanisms, there is no matrix cavity growth in fatigue. Moreover, micro-cavitation and cracks are detected in fatigued specimens. These fatigue mechanisms are illustrated and described hereunder.

4.1.1 Fibre failure

This phenomenon is widespread in the material. Systematic fibre crossing near any fibre failure has to be noticed, as shown in figure 7. This fact suggests that important overstress is locally induced by microstructure singularities.

Figure 7 : Fibre failures (specimen fatigued until 75% of its estimated life)

4.1.2 Damage at fibre ends

Damage at fibre ends has been observed during both quasi-static and fatigue testing, as presented in figure 8. Associated damage markers are described by the following geometry: volume inferior to $520 \mu\text{m}^3$ (volume of a sphere with a diameter equivalent to fibres diameter) and low aspect ratio, for cylindrical to spherical markers.

Figure 8 : Damage at fibre ends (specimen fatigued until 95% of its estimated life)

4.1.3 Debonding

Debonding is also observed among fatigue damage mechanisms (cf. figure 9a). It has been pointed out that this mechanism is not consistently initiated at fibre ends, contrary to usual description found in literature. Indeed, this phenomenon is activated by fibre crossing at the fibre-matrix interface. Damage markers associated to debonding are recognizable by their high aspect ratio (superior to four from observations), corresponding to lengthy markers.

Figure 9 : a) Debonding and b) Micro-cavitation (specimen fatigued at 95% of its estimated life)

4.1.4 Micro-cavitation

This matrix mechanism has been observed during fatigue testing, as shown in figure 9b, and is probably activated by long-term stress. This phenomenon brings precious information about damage evolution of the matrix. Damage markers associated to micro-cavitation are determined by a maximal length of 5μm and an aspect ratio close to one.

4.1.5 Crack

Microcracks and cracks have been observed in fatigued specimens. These lengthy markers arise from short distance interactions between nearby damage markers. Their development seems to be highly dictated by the local microstructure orientation. Indeed, cracks orientation tends to be perpendicular to the macroscopic tensile direction, until they run into a fibre. There, depending on the closest damage marker, the crack growth can coalesce with this marker or can be stopped if the distance or the deviation is too important. These markers are defined by their high aspect ratio (>8) and length (>50μm) to represent this very long damage mechanism.

Figure 10 : Crack (specimen fatigued at 95% of its estimated life)

4.2 Application to the observed volumes

Figure 11 presents the synthesis of geometrical thresholds used to distinguish damage markers depending on the identified mechanisms. No matrix cavity growth has been noticed. The fact is that maximal applied stress is inferior during fatigue testing than during quasi-static testing, whereas cavity growth is particularly driven by it. Also, microtomographed microstructures are all different with interrupted fatigue test procedure. For this reason, it was not possible to count the number of fibre failures as during *in situ* tensile test procedure. Fibre failures are therefore not differentiated from fibre ends damage markers.

Figure 11 : Fatigue mechanisms classification based on geometrical aspects of damage markers

Micro-cavitation, fibre ends damage and fibre failure, debonding and cracks are quantified by the number of counted damage markers. These quantities are presented in figure 12 for each identified mechanism. Micro-cavitation has been activated during fatigue testing. This matrix damage mechanism seems linked with long term stress application. The number of markers associated to micro-cavitation grows during the fatigue test as presented in figure 12a. Another damage mechanism in the matrix is the crack formation. As explained in the paragraph 4.1.5, cracks appear where there is short distance interaction between pre-existing damage markers. This implies that microstructure plays an important role on the growth of these markers and therefore, on their number. In the case of shell in 0° oriented specimen, non-broken fibres constitute obstacles to crack growth and lead to an increase of the crack number, as seen in figure 12d.

Concerning damage at the fibre-matrix interface, the number of markers corresponding to damage at fibre ends and fibre failures has a fast development for the three specimen orientations, shown in figure 12b. Its quantity is more associated to the number of fibres than to their orientation. Indeed, the fibre geometry creates an overstress at fibre ends, where there is no sizing to improve mechanical

properties of the interface. Debonding is also mostly activated by fibre crossing and not only by the difference between fibre orientation and tensile macroscopic direction. Figure 12c shows that the evolution of the number of damage markers is important for 0° oriented specimens and subtle for 45° and 90° oriented specimens. This is probably due to the fact that distinction between debonding and crack is not totally perfect.

Figure 12 : Damage mechanism density evolution depending on specimen orientation

5 CONCLUSIONS

Damage mechanisms due to quasi-static and fatigue testing have been observed by X-ray microtomography. Observed damage markers are differentiated by their geometric aspects (length, volume and aspect ratio) and associated to each identified mechanism. This differentiation allows to quantify the development of these mechanisms at different levels of damage. Damage mechanisms kinetics are deduced for global observed volumes and bring precious information for physically based micro-mechanical modelling. At the micron scale, local microstructure singularities have been pointed out (fibre ends and fibres crossing). An overstress is probably due to these microstructural singularities, leading to damage initiation. Future work will determine strain and stress fields and compare them with observations in order to estimate levels of activation of each mechanism at this scale.

REFERENCES

- [1] J.L. Thomason. *The influence of fibre properties on the performance of glass fibre reinforced polyamide 6,6*. Composites Science and Technology, 59:2315–2328, 1999.
- [2] J.L. Thomason. *The influence of fibre length, diameter and concentration on the modulus of glass fibre reinforced polyamide 6,6*. Composites: Part A, 39:1732–1738, 2008.
- [3] J. J. Horst, J. L. Spoormaker. *Mechanisms of fatigue in short glass fibre reinforced polyamide 6*. Polymer Engineering & Science, 36(22):2718–2726, November 1996.
- [4] J. J. Horst, J. L. Spoormaker, *Fatigue fracture mechanisms and fractography of short-glassfibre-reinforced polyamide 6*, Journal of materials science, vol. 32, no. 14, pp. 3641–3651, 1997.
- [5] A. Kak, M. Slaney. *Principles of computerized tomographic imaging*. IEEE, New York, 1988.
- [6] S. Barbouchi, V. Bellenger, A. Tcharkhtchi, Ph. Castaing, T. Jollivet. *Effect of water on the fatigue behaviour of a pa66/glass fibers composite material*. Journal of Materials Science, 42(6):2181–2188, February 2007.
- [7] M.F. Arif, F. Meraghni, Y. Chemisky, N. Despringre, G. Robert. *In situ damage mechanisms investigation of pa66gf30 composite: effect of relative humidity*. Composites: Part B, 58:487–495, 2014.
- [8] A. Bernasconi, F. Cosmi, D. Dreossi. *Local anisotropy analysis of injection moulded fibre reinforced polymer composites*, Composites Science and Technology, Volume 68, Issue 12, September 2008, Pages 2574–2581
- [9] H. Rolland, N. Saintier, G. Robert, *Damage mechanisms into SGFR thermoplastic during in situ microtomographic tensile tests*. ECCM16 Conference, Seville-Spain, 2014